

TEACHING GRAMMAR THROUGH AUTHENTIC TEXTS**Elchiboyeva Nigorbonu,***The student of the faculty foreign languages
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Annotation: Teaching grammar has been always the point of discussions for many years. Therefore there are many controversies on the matters of teaching grammar.

As it is known, the schools and lyceums in our country prepare learners to enter the Higher Educational Establishments, where the entrance examinations are based on knowing the grammar rules.

However, we should teach student not only to do grammar tests, but also correctly use the grammar rules while speaking. Students often complain that they know all the grammar, but they are still incorrect when they speak and cannot use properly grammar rules in their speech.

Using communication activities to teach grammar can offer variety to the students and cater to the needs of learners who are keen to develop their ability to use English. It also provides opportunities for teachers to give systematic feedback on students' errors.

In the classroom we need to provide learners with opportunities to understand the grammatical system of the target language and relate this grammatical system to the meanings it conveys in communication.

There are many ways of teaching grammar in communicative approach. In this article we want to present the advantages of teaching grammar through authentic texts.

As it is known, authentic texts give more opportunity to learners to acquire the language as it is.

There are the following advantages in teaching grammar through authentic texts as providing co-textual information, allowing learners to deduce the meaning of unfamiliar grammatical items from the context; if the texts are authentic they can show how the item is used in real communication; as well as grammar input, texts provide vocabulary input, skills practice, and exposure to features of text organization; their use in the classroom is good preparation for independent study; if the texts come from the students themselves, they may be more engaging and their language features therefore more memorable. One more benefit of it is that introducing grammar, using the authentic texts should be taught together with teaching reading, listening, writing and speaking skills. Involving all the skills learners grasp the language and alongside with it grammar will be in the centre.

However, with advantages we can also mention some disadvantages. The first one is the difficulty of the text. Some teachers attempt to use a dense newspaper article with low level students. The linguistic load of unfamiliar vocabulary and syntactic complexity can make such texts impenetrable, and ultimately very demotivating. Considering that, the teacher should choose the texts appropriate to the level and also they should be adequate with the syllabus of the discipline taught. One of the alternative is to use simplified texts as they may give a misleading impression as to how the language item is naturally used, again defeating the purpose of using texts. Not all texts will be of equal interest to students. Therefore the teacher should select the materials considering learners' interest.

The learners are to achieve a functional command of a foreign language, they will need to be able to understand and produce not just isolated sentences, but whole texts in that language. The language is context-sensitive, which means that an utterance becomes fully intelligible only when it is placed in its context. That is why, when we give grammar through context it will be more efficient to acquire the language structure and use grammar rules appropriately.

Teaching grammar through the authentic texts will give learners opportunity to master their communicative skills too. The authentic texts tend to make easy understanding and displaying the specific features of grammar.

Thus, the aim of the teacher in teaching grammar through the authentic texts is to select the necessary materials related to the level, interest of learners.